

SPORADIC INSIGHTS. THE PAULISTA RESIDENTIAL ARCHITECTURE IN ITALIAN MAGAZINES (1930-1960) - CONSIDERATIONS ON THE MARGINS

ESPORÁDICAS INTUIÇÕES. A ARQUITETURA RESIDENCIAL PAULISTA NAS REVISTAS ITALIANAS (1930-1960) - CONSIDERAÇÕES À MARGEM

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Resumo

A atenção dada pelas revistas italianas à produção arquitetônica do Brasil no século XX foi várias vezes destacada por estudiosos, especialmente brasileiros. A partir dessas reflexões e da pesquisa realizada pela autora sobre a Escola de São Paulo, este texto pretende “reabrir o caso”, focando especificamente na divulgação da produção de residências entre 1930 e 1960. Nos anos de desenvolvimento e expansão da cidade, são experimentados e difundidos novos modelos de “habitar”, nos quais os caracteres distintivos das marcas paulistas aparecem imediatamente identificáveis. Diante de um processo tão criativo e construtivo, as revistas italianas parecem não compreender a revolução arquitetônica paulista, concentrando-se mais frequentemente em projetistas conhecidos e principalmente relacionados à esfera italiana. No panorama paulistano, elementos imprescindíveis para uma contextualização histórica e arquitetônica são: a difusão de posições modernistas; a afirmação do Concretismo; o envolvimento de Artigas no Partido Comunista; a busca constante de uma dialética entre o compromisso político e a liberdade do processo criativo; a austeridade arquitetônica traduzida em projeto social; as preocupações coletivas mais do que as estéticas. A partir daqui se dá a necessidade de uma releitura.

Palavras-chave: Movimento Moderno. Arquitetura paulista e italiana. Habitação.

Abstract

Over the course of the 20th century Italian publications devoted much interest to Brazilian architecture, a fact that scholars have often emphasized, especially in Brazil. This, along with the research I conducted on the São Paulo School, is the starting point of the present text, which focuses on the way Italian observers described the housing output in São Paulo between 1930 and 1960. As the city grew, new housing models were tested and established, with features that unmistakably identified the Paulista tendencies. It was an exceptionally creative and productive phase, but Italian publications seemed unable to understand that São Paulo's architecture was undergoing a revolution, and they just kept focusing on renowned, well-established architects that, often, were also somehow connected to Italian architecture. To give some historical and architectural context to the revolution that took place in São Paulo, we must bear in mind a few facts: the Modernist tendencies were gaining ground; Concretism was by then well established; Artigas got involved with the Communist Party; there was a constant pursuit of balance between political activism and creative freedom; and, since social welfare was more important than aesthetics, austere architecture emerged as the expression of a social project. The need to integrate all these factors seems to warrant a new analysis.

Keywords: Modern Movement. Paulista and Italian Architecture. Housing.

Introduction

In 2007, Casabella (n.276) was the first major architecture magazine in Italy to publish a long essay on the very symbol of São Paulo architecture: the Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning designed by João Batista Vilanova Artigas and Carlos Cascaldi (1961-1968), a masterpiece that conflates social commitment and spatial continuity, static, aesthetic and ethic relations.

It took a very long time indeed and it's hard to understand why, especially now, after more than a decade since Casabella and other magazines have started to keep Italian professionals up to date with the elegant and socially conscious Paulista production, both modern and contemporary.

Brazilian critics started to write about it in the 1970s, when Artigas and other architects' oeuvres were recognized as having peculiar ideological and creative features that were influenced by the Modern Movement, whose ideas they developed and updated, setting themselves apart from the Rio de Janeiro School.

The two cities have a different approach, which can be summarized by Rio de Janeiro's lavish curves on the one hand, and the poetic essentiality of São Paulo's straight lines on the other, but they still have some affinities: shapes shift as needs vary and new values arise.

The project that GrupoSP presented to the recently launched 16th Venice International Architecture Exhibition could be taken as further evidence of this. The Unnamed Spaces installation is defined by the simplicity of the primordial signs, the curve and the straight line, as incisively explained by Flavio Motta, who said that 'unnamed spaces' were the free and open spaces which shelter life's unpredictability. The whole installation is a celebration of the designed void that São Paulo architects, resorting to great structural light span, used to create continuous and undivided spaces, buildings that blend into the urban

context, a synergy between the individual and the community.

These solutions are not confined to a single kind of building, and are indeed adopted for housing, schools, work and leisure spaces.

This means that it is possible to employ the same compositional and executive strategy for many different purposes, with no need for multiple methodologies; and this is another reason why we can examine São Paulo's architecture as a whole through the analysis of individual building models. So I selected a number of residential buildings, giving priority to those that appeared on Italian architecture magazines.

A first distinctive practice is the very endeavour of defining what exactly a housing space is and what its relation to urban space consists in. A full theorization of it will appear in Artigas's 1969 essay *Arquitetura e Construção*.

Starting from the construction of houses, that is, of very small areas, humans try to appropriate their environment, made of roads, bridges, train stations and airports.

These structures become complementary to the houses and, through them, the housing space becomes universal, that's why "The city is a house. The house is a city" (Artigas, 1969, p.17). In this context, infrastructures and services, being closely connected to the private space, contribute to determine the urban space, which then becomes a home for a new community, actively affecting the way citizens interact: "Cities as homes. Homes as cities" (Artigas, 1969, p.17).

The research into housing is the first thing that set São Paulo's architecture apart from its European and North American models, connecting it to its own cultural and architectural heritage now filled with new meanings, both social and ethical.

In the 1920s, young Brazilian architects had embraced Functionalism, because it offered them the first real possibility of getting rid of their country's colonial past. There was a widespread desire for chan-

ge that led to see architecture as a cultural matter (Motta, 1960), and this had to do with both space and materials.

Nevertheless, modern Brazil was not exempt from extremely formal works, but after World War II a new trend set in and the old models, until then undisputed, underwent a radical transformation.

In São Paulo, the quest for national identity drew together many disciplines and, in the early 1950s, a group of artists and intellectuals brought back the Anthropophagic Movement, originally started by Oswald de Andrade in 1928.

There was, at the time, a climate of creative unrest supported by the progressive left. This was the hectic background against which Artigas started wondering how architects could contribute to the social transformation of the country: architecture was not to be seen as a work of art but as the cultural expression of a people, an era, a moment in history. It had to tackle the past, which, if necessary, could and had to be challenged.

Italian architects, critics and intellectuals didn't realize the magnitude of this transformation, that's why Italian magazines did not register its outcomes.

To understand the reasons underlying this undeniable, albeit unwitting, ostracism, we must go back in time and retrace the steps that allowed the Modern Movement to gain ground and go through a new, peculiarly Brazilian interpretation; we will then look into the 1950s and 60s, when mainstream Italian observers failed to analyze, understand and divulge this considerable and varied production that was rising and growing right before them.

Explaining the ostracismo

Italian magazines ignored São Paulo's original input, probably because they were reluctant to question mainstream architectural historiography, which misrepresented mere blurred lines as entirely different

categories.

As it's been noted, within the vast Latin American architectural scene Italy paid special attention to São Paulo's output, sometimes equated to the country's as a whole. But the focus of Italy's interest was the feats of Italian architects working in Brazil's economic capital, whose presence was partly due to the significant Italian migration that took place after WWII.

The most emblematic case is that of Rino Levi, who received a lot of publicity by many magazines throughout his career. In 1938, in *Architettura* - whose editor was Marcello Piacentini - Pasquale Carbonara wrote a piece on three projects by Levi¹, emphasizing the fact that Levi, a Brazilian architect of Italian descent, had been educated at the School of Architecture in Rome. This, along with his work with Piacentini and his atelier, and the undeniable merits of his projects and teachings, explains why Italian critics were so keen on him.

The European influence on Levi's early work is evident in Luis Medici House. The house rests on the hillside, deep in a lush tropical garden; it has clear functional distinctions, favoured by the quadrangular plan, whose only exception is the rounded corner of the living room. Painted white, supported in part by pilotis, and with a ribbon window that runs along the living room, the house presents a plastic coherence that is reminiscent of Erich Mendelsohn; it is also influenced by Le Corbusier's and, not least, the Italian lesson; the gable roof partially hidden behind a horizontal cornice recalls instead the solution adopted by Gregori Warchavchik for the modernist house in rua Santa Cruz (1927)², a choice justified by the technical limitations of the time, as explained by Anelli e Contier (2014). But in spite of the interest elicited by Levi, Italian critics failed to emphasize his role in spreading

1 i.e. Luis Medici House, Columbus Building and Ufa Palace Cinema, all in São Paulo.

2 Which makes a brief appearance in the Italian magazine *Domus* (1993, n.64) with a couple of pictures and a few paragraphs.

the principles of the Modern Movement in Brazil, a role that is now widely acknowledged. As noted by Bruno Zevi among others, those principles reached Brazil in 1936, when Le Corbusier went to Rio de Janeiro to advise on the design of the new Ministério de Educação e Saúde (Zevi, 1955).

In 1925 when Warchavchik's manifesto *Acerca da Arquitetura Moderna* was first published in the Italian newspaper *Il Piccolo* and, later that year, in the carioca *Correio de Manhã*, Italy reacted with indifference. Published that same year, on the 15th of October, Rino Levi's manifesto *A arquitetura e a estética das cidades* suffered the same fate, despite being written in Italy and sent from there to the Estado de São Paulo³.

Some of the features that will come to define São Paulo's architecture appear for the first time in that manifesto: practicality and economy, a predominantly volumetric approach, simple lines and absence of decorative elements, use of *béton brut*.

In line with what he learned in Italy, though, Levi proposed a modernization that didn't require a radical break with the classical tradition, even while acknowledging the huge opportunities the Modern Movement offered to Brazil. Such opportunities, seen as means to cater to the needs of the country, were central to Levi's research and especially to his plans for single-family homes, where he worked on the relationship between house and nature, as exemplified by his own residence in São Paulo. In 1947, *Domus* n.222 □ edited by Ernesto Natan Rogers □ featured a mostly photographic presentation of this house along with its layout. The pictures and the layout show a house set deep in a lush Brazilian foliage, with green areas that are accessible from both private and communal spaces (Figure 1)⁴. This building too has clear functional distinctions; living areas and sleeping areas are divided by

3 Zevi would mention it only 1975 on *L'Espresso*.

4 Figure 1: Rino Levi's House. Credits: *Domus*, n. 222, p. 70-73, September 1947.

a long hallway, with a fully furnished service area that serves as further demarcation and diaphragm between the main areas.

The greenhouse is another interstitial space, separating the building from nature, enclosed but at the same time with openings both in the perimeter walls and the roof. Wind, rain and sun - the sunlight filters through horizontal concrete slats - become an integral part of the composition, ubiquitous in São Paulo's architecture and culminating in Artigas's 'pop' house: Casa Elza Berquó (1967). In this case it is nature itself, in the form of tree trunks, that holds up the patio roof and marks the imaginary divide between interior and exterior space.

It is a proper patio house, which is unusual for São Paulo. This kind of building - quintessentially Spanish and, more generally, Mediterranean - arrives in Brazil partly thanks to Bernard Rudofsky's Arnstein and Frontini Houses (Figure 2)⁵. *Domus* (n.234, 1949) fancifully described them as "islands [...] with secret patios", which proves the enduring appeal of São Paulo's architecture, reinforced by Rudofsky's collaborations with Italian architects such as Gio Ponti and Luigi Cosenza⁶.

This same introversion pattern, in contrast with the tendencies of the Paulista metropolis, can be found, albeit with significant variations, in Doctor T's House by Ponti, published in *Domus* n.283 (1953, figure 3)⁷.

It is an interesting project for many reasons: the angular line, achieved through a series of short staggered planes, helps defining the segments' different functions and creating a dynamism both internal and between inside and outside spaces, highlighted by the relatively small differences in height. The double-height living room spreads into the

5 Figure 2: Bernard Rudofsky, Arnstein (1941) and Frontini (1940) Houses. Credits: *Domus*, n. 234, p. 1-9, April 1949.

6 For a detailed examination of the changes that the Mediterranean patio went through in modern Brazilian architecture, see Anelli (2003).

7 Figure 3: Gio Ponti, Doctor T's House. Credits: *Domus*, n. 283, p. 8-11, June 1953.

garden and, through its window walls, creates a visual continuity with the outdoors. The building is situated lengthwise on the lot, which is surrounded by a staggering 6.20 meters wall that, as Ponti explained, was meant to hide the neighbouring houses and the outside “confusion” (Ponti, 1963).

The Italian architect’s introverted choice diverged from the prevalent local tendencies, brilliantly summarized in the words of Paulo Mendes da Rocha: “The essence of the house is not the house, it’s the house’s address, the coexistence of the urban space” (Mendes da Rocha, 1990), which means that even purely residential architecture must be understood as part of a wider, choral and social concept.

This concept took the form of buildings with both communal and residential functions and generated a rich experimental field in São Paulo. Even Lina Bo Bardi and Pier Luigi Nervi took part in it with the Guajanazes project (Figure 4)⁸, that *Domus* published in 1953 (n.282).

Two tall buildings stand above the big, multi-story basement that would house an auditorium, two theatres and the tv studio of Assis Chateaubriand, who commissioned the complex.

The Italian architects designed a residential infrastructure with distinct residential cells, like single-family homes. The apartments have balconies suspended by steel wire ropes - the perimeter edge extends beyond the structure - and receive light from the sides, through double-height patio that also convey the light up to the central distribution hallway. Inside the apartments, the only distinction is between served space - with no further subdivision - and servant space. On each floor there are four kind of apartments, two of which minimal, intended for one or two people. The main concept was, as a matter of fact, the spatial flexibility of the domestic environment and the minimal housing, an idea that became central to the Italian and European debate after

8 Figure 4: Lina Bo Bardi, Pier Luigi Nervi, Guajanazes Building. Credits: *Domus*, n. 282, p. 4-7, May 1953.

World War II and in the following years.

By the mid-1950s a new trend developed in the Italian press: Brasília's great adventure had begun.

The Brasília 'Syndrome'

In 1957, when Lucio Costa's Pilot Plan was presented, the reflection about Brasília's urban structure and architecture took over Italian magazines, sparking a long-lasting debate.

In the magazine L'Espresso, that had a weekly architecture column since 1955 and for almost fifty years, Zevi wrote many articles about the new capital city, which would later be collected into the series *Cronache di Architettura*.

The famous Italian critic didn't spare Costa and Niemeyer from his harsh judgement, both before and after visiting Brasília's construction site in 1959, during the Extraordinary AICA Congress, when he also visited Rio de Janeiro and São Paulo. Between 1959 and 1960 he published four short pieces about his journey; the last of them focused on the Paulista capital and, more specifically, on its Biennale. According to Zevi, the Biennale played a pivotal role in promoting the cultural revisionism that was developing in the city, whose architecture gave him an impression of disillusionment and uncertainty, as compared to what was prevalent in the Carioca School. For Zevi, the Modern Movement could be revived only in São Paulo, and this proves that he understood the ideological and formal process that was underway there (Zevi, 1960).

However, the group of Rio de Janeiro architects - Niemeyer, Costa, Burle Marx, Reidy - would still play a crucial role in defining and publicizing Brazil's architecture.

And yet, in *Introduzione al Brasile*, a piece published in 1960 by the Italian magazine *Zodiac*, Flavio Motta warned that an interpretation solely based on a small - albeit important - set of events might end up

producing “formalistic judgments” (Motta, 1960, p. 61).

This issue of the magazine was instrumental in making Brazil’s architecture known to the Italian public (Costa, 2010), it is therefore worth spending some more time looking into it.

It is immediately apparent that no clear distinction was made in the magazine between São Paulo’s and Rio de Janeiro’s approach. Bruno Alfieri saw Artigas’s work as part of “a dramatically contrary architecture” (Alfieri, 1960, p.97) as compared to the Carioca one.

Artigas’s forms, “raw and anti-pleasant” (Alfieri, 1960, p.97), are likened to those of Smithson and Viganò, a comparison that Artigas dreaded because, as Ruth Zein put it, it meant interpreting São Paulo’s architecture as a seamless extension of what was going on internationally, rather than acknowledging its peculiar features (Zein, 2002).

Even Frank Lloyd Wright’s influence on Artigas was taken by Alfieri as a stance against Le Corbusier’s rationalism. On the contrary, Artigas recognized Wright’s socially and ideologically subversive charge, the same the he was trying to carry forward in Brazil, and thought of him as the epitome of what an architect’s mission should be: “to give real substance to the thought of the people” (apud Artigas, Lira, 2004, p.99)⁹. Alfieri then examined Rubens de Mendonça House (1958), describing the projecting façade as a manifesto for brutalist architecture while ignoring the evident, albeit limited, motifs that connect it to the Neo-avantgardes. Decorated by Rebolo Gonzales with blue and white triangles, it is clearly reminiscent of Luiz Sacilotto’s optical art: the architect wanted to express his own “political, aesthetical and social coexistence with the Concrete Art Group” (apud Artigas, Lira, 2004, p.212)¹⁰. This work anticipates the motif of the elevated volume cantilevered by few supports that Artigas would further develop in the

9 ARTIGAS, João Batista Vilanova. Frank Lloyd Wright [1869-1959]. São Paulo: Cosac&Naify, 2004, p.99.

10 ARTIGAS, João Batista Vilanova. Segunda argüição. São Paulo: Cosac&Naify, 2004, p.212.

following years, but its prevalent features are deliberately Concretist, but in a way that is more formal than substantial.

Flávio Motta, in his Zodiac article, had clearly explained where to look to better understand Brazilian architecture, but its complex and elaborate context had remained unexamined.

Three years later, it was again Zodiac (1963, n.11) that published an article on the latest developments in São Paulo's architecture, penned by Geraldo Ferraz. After its inauguration in 1960, Brasília had taken center stage, so it seems no coincidence that Ferraz, who advocated the Paulista origins of modern Brazilian architecture, chose to write about the Cidade Universitaria Armando de Salles Oliveira (CUASO), the campus that was under construction in São Paulo. As a matter of fact, the campus itself was going to be a sort of newly founded city.

Ferraz took the opportunity to examine the campus's urban planning and to make a survey of the designers that populated São Paulo's architecture scene at the time.

Carioca monumental style never took hold at CUASO, nor in the rest of the city, because architecture's aim here has always been to tackle the problems of the megalopolis.

Over the course of the years, São Paulo's architecture revealed a unique ability to elaborate new, creative solutions, always focused on the needs of the city and its social and cultural issues. It's been able to diversify more and more the building materials, while always sticking to an idea of architecture whose roots can be traced, at least in part, to the Modern Movement.

One of São Paulo architects' main goals was to tackle and solve the problems that arise in defining the public space, and the construction of the campus, a place that would accommodate a very large community, presented them with the exciting challenge of bringing together learning spaces, communal residential quarters, offices and ceremonial spaces.

The design of the residential quarters (1961-1963), by Eduardo

Kneesse de Mello, Joel Ramalho Jr. and Sidney de Oliveira (Figure 5)¹¹, is the occasion to explore the combination of communal housing and cultural growth. The complex sits at the very centre of CUASO, and is made up of ten residential blocks, six with a cast-in-situ structure and four in prestressed reinforced concrete, a technique which was rarely adopted in São Paulo at the time. This is hardly surprising, because Kneesse de Mello was a firm supporter of industrialization as a means to meet the ever-growing housing demand.

The six-storey blocks are positioned in a staggered line along the central covered walkway that connects the ground-floors - which are open and supported by pilotis - to the adjoining communal spaces.

Believing that there must be a synergy between the houses of a city and the city itself, Kneesse de Mello designed a sort of urban microcosm. Individual spaces gave way to intensely shared ones, as exemplified by the decision to create only mini-apartments intended for three students. Minimal housing was once again a central theme, along with a careful and measured control over private spaces, reinforced by specifically designed furniture that allowed students some privacy in a mostly shared environment.

Like CUASO itself, this place had a clear cultural and social goal, inspired by São Paulo University's fundamental principles: advancing progress, elevating spirits, training professionals, and achieving the social aim of promoting science, literature and arts.

Lastly, the FAU building, "rigorously sincere, neatly disposed", will be the place where "the University will form the continuity of architectural work in São Paulo" (Ferraz, 1963, p.72).

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11 Figure 5: Eduardo Kneesse de Mello, et al., Residential Complex USP. Credits: Arquigrafia, available in: <http://www.arquigrafia.org.br/photos/1909>. Acropole, n. 303, p. 93-101, February 1964, available in: <http://www.acropole.fau.usp.br/edicao/303>.

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